

MODERNIZATION OF COLLEGE GOING TRIBAL STUDENTS

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Paper Received On: 21 June 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 25 July 2024

Published On: 01 August 2024

Abstract

Modernization has many denotations and carries a heavy weight and connotations. The term modern refers to follow a new approach, a new outlook; a new attitude for the objects, situations, ideology and people in life. Professor Jacobs (1971) explains “modernization as the maximization of the potential of the society.” (Cited at Chaudhary, A. (2017). Objective of the research is to study the college going female tribal students with reference to hill/plain area and science/non science. Findings of the study indicate that Female tribal students of hill area were highly modernized in terms of position of women dimension while they were least modernized in terms of education dimension. On the other hand, female tribal students of plain area were highly modernized in terms of position of women dimension while they were least modernized in terms socio-religious dimension.

Introduction

Change is the law of nature and in human society change always takes place. Life has always been changing. Sometimes the speed of these changes is slow while some times they are rapid and drastic. All spheres of living things are changing. This change is termed as modernization. Modernization has many denotations and carries a heavy weight and connotations. The term modern refers to follow a new approach, a new outlook; a new attitude for the objects, situations, ideology and people in life. **Professor Jacobs (1971)** explains “**modernization as the maximization of the potential of the society.**” (Cited at Chaudhary, A. (2017))

No one can deny the fact that modernization affects the different aspects of people’s life. Young students are the most vulnerable group suffering from the negative effects of modernization. Traditional values and norms are seemed to be violated by rapid social changes which results in increasing the crime rate. Speed and level of modernization lead to variations in the crime

rates across countries (*Clinard, M.B. & Abbott, D.J., 1973*). Modernization affects the life of people in both ways negatively as well as positively. Modernization has created such a materially rich world where people have access to material things and they can make their lives more comfortable and easy. In modernized society, women have more opportunity and freedom for their development. It also helps to liberate oppressed minority groups. On the other hand, modernization put a negative effect on our society. It breakups the social ties that bound people together in tradition societies. The people do not feel connected to one another. This can lead to such problems as crime and breakup of family groups.

Tribal people play an important part in the construction of cultural heritage of India. They are considered as the true habitants of India. Each tribal community is distinguished from each other in their traditional and cultural norms. According to the Article 342 of the Indian Constitution there are six hundred and ninety seven tribes as notified by the Central Government (*India Tourism Catalog.com*). The tribal groups of people have been notified to reside in more than one state. North India also encompasses many tribes. In Dehradun district of Uttarakhand, five tribes are found namely - Bhotia, Tharu, Jaunsari, Buxa and Van Rawat (a forest dwelling tribe). There is a great diversity in the habitat, population, ethnicity, socio-cultural norms and practices, modes of livelihoods. Due to the technological advancements, industrialization, westernization and modernization the living style and thinking style of tribal people undergo a change. In the present study, the investigator tried to examine the study of modernization of the college going tribal girls students.

Statement of the Problem

“Modernization of College Going Tribal Students”

Operational Definition of Key Terms

The most important part of the scientific study of any phenomenon is a definition which will permit the rese

Tribal Students

In the present study, college going tribal students means those students who belong to tribal area and are studying in the undergraduate courses in various disciplines in the degree colleges of district Dehradun.

Modernization

In simple words modernization means to render something old fashioned up to date. The word modernization is derived from Latin word ‘moud’ which mean modern. Modernization is that process which reshapes the out of date things to suit the requirement of the continuous changing

world. Basically, modernization is a term from sociology which is used to denote complex process of social change from traditional way of living and thinking. The term modernization is many times thought as or considered as westernization. But a westernized man may not be necessarily a modern man.

Modernization is that process which brings positive changes in attitudes, beliefs and values, incorporates rational outlook, openness to innovation and changes, secular attitudes, belief in human efficacy and expression of personal opinion on the public issues, acceptance of democratic norms rather than past and exposure to new experience. Thus, change in ways of perceiving, expressing and behaving may be termed as modernization. In general terms, **“to modernize” means “to render sometime old fashioned up to date” or “reshape something out of date to suit the requirements of modern times” (Chodak, 1983).**

Thus, modernization refers to a deeper change in man’s way of thinking and feeling; a change in his whole attitude to life’s problem, the society and the universe. Modernization means the attitudinal changes in spheres of belief and behaviour. In the present study, the change in the four dimensions i.e. (a) socio-religious, (b) marriage, (c) position of women, and (d) education is considered as the modernization of college going students. In this way, modernization means the scores obtained by tribal students on **‘Modernization Scale’** developed by **Raghavendra S. Singh, Amar Nath Tripathi and Ramjee Lal.**

Objectives of the Study

For the present study, following objectives are determined:

1. To study the modernization of college going female tribal students.
2. To study the modernization of college going female tribal students of hill and plain area.
3. To study the modernization of college going female tribal students of science and non-science stream.
4. To compare the modernization of college going female tribal students of hill and plain area.
5. To compare the modernization of college going female tribal students of science and non-science stream.

Hypotheses:

1. There will be no significant difference in the modernization of college going female tribal students of hill and plain area

2. To compare the modernization of college going female tribal students of science and non- science stream.

Delimitation of the Study

The delimitations of the study are as follows:

1. The present study has been delimited to district Dehradun of Uttarakhand.
2. This study has involved the college going girls students who are currently living in the hill and plain area of district Dehradun.
3. The study has been delimited to college going students who are studying in the undergraduate courses.

Population of the Study

For this study, all the college going female tribal students who are currently residing in the hill and plain area of district Dehradun are taken as the population of the study. The students who have passed Intermediate and are studying in undergraduate courses are the population of the present study.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The researcher selected 300 college going students randomly. College going students who are currently residing in the hill and plain area of district Dehradun have been taken in this study. 300 females (150 science students and 150 non-science students) have been selected for this study. The sampling frame work is as follows:

Tools Used

Following standardized tools have been used for the present study:

Modernization Scale developed by Raghavendra S. Singh, Amar Nath Tripathi and Ramjee Lal.

Result and Interpretation

To study the modernization of college going female tribal students.

Table – 1: Mean and S.D. of the Modernization of Female Tribal Students

Modernization	Female		
	N	Mean	S.D.
Socio-Religious	300	27.37	7.10
Marriage	300	28.06	7.03
Position of Women	300	32.47	8.60
Education	300	28.59	7.47

The table no.1 shows mean and S.D. of the modernization of female tribal students. The mean score of socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions of modernization of female tribal students are 27.37, 28.06, 32.47 and 28.59 respectively. These mean scores indicate that female tribal students have average level of modernization on socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions. Female tribal students have highest level of modernization on position of women dimension while they are least modernized in socio-religious dimension.

To study the modernization of college going female tribal students of hill and plain area.

Table -2: Mean and S.D. of the Modernization of Female Tribal Students of Hill and Plain Area

Modernization	Students of Hill Area			Students of Plain Area		
	N	Mean	S.D.	N	Mean	S.D.
Socio-Religious	150	28.20	6.56	150	27.22	8.03
Marriage	150	27.89	7.32	150	27.59	7.50
Position of Women	150	29.65	9.93	150	30.80	8.86
Education	150	25.81	7.74	150	29.10	7.80

The table no 2 shows mean and S.D. of the modernization of tribal students of hill and plain area. The mean score of socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions of modernization of tribal students of hill area are 28.20, 27.89, 29.65 and 25.81 respectively. These mean scores indicate that tribal students of hill area have average level of modernization on socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions. Tribal students of hill area have highest level of modernization on position of women dimension while they are least modernized in education dimension.

The mean score of socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions of modernization of tribal students of plain area are 27.22, 27.59, 30.80 and 29.10 respectively. These mean scores indicate that tribal students of plain area have average level of modernization on socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions. Tribal students of plain area have highest level of modernization on position of women dimension while they are least modernized in socio-religious dimension.

To study the modernization of college going female tribal students of science and non-science stream.

Table – 3: Mean and S.D. of the Modernization of Female Tribal Students of Science and Non-Science Stream

Modernization	Students of Science Stream			Students of Non-Science Stream		
	N	Mean	S.D.	N	Mean	S.D.
Socio-Religious	150	28.07	7.86	150	27.25	6.93
Marriage	150	27.84	7.85	150	27.61	6.96
Position of Women	150	30.31	10.00	150	30.27	8.70
Education	150	28.31	8.61	150	26.94	7.15

The table no 3 shows mean and S.D. of the modernization of tribal students of science and non-science stream. The mean score of socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions of modernization of tribal students of science stream are 28.07, 27.84, 30.31 and 28.31 respectively. These mean scores indicate that tribal students of science stream have average level of modernization on socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions. Tribal students of science stream have highest level of modernization on position of women dimension while they are least modernized in marriage dimension.

The mean score of socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions of modernization of tribal students of non-science stream are 27.25, 27.61, 30.27 and 26.94 respectively. These mean scores indicate that tribal students of non-science stream have average level of modernization on socio-religious, marriage, position of women and education dimensions. Tribal students of non-science stream have highest level of modernization on position of women dimension while they are least modernized in education dimension.

To compare the modernization of college going female tribal students of hill and plain area.

Table – 4: Comparison of Modernization of College going Female Tribal Students of Hill and Plain Area

Dimensions of Modernization	Area	Mean	S.D.	df	t-value	Result
Socio-Religious	Hill	28.20	6.58	598	1.598	NS
	Plain	27.23	8.04			
Marriage	Hill	27.89	7.33	598	0.486	NS
	Plain	27.59	7.51			
Position of Women	Hill	29.65	9.95	598	1.492	NS
	Plain	30.80	8.87			
Education	Hill	25.81	7.76	598	5.141**	S
	Plain	29.10	7.81			

** = Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance.

S = Significant

NS = Not Significant

The table no. 4 presents the comparison of modernization of college going tribal students of hill and plain area. The obtained t-values for modernization in terms of education dimension ($t = 5.141$) has been found significant at 0.01 level of significance at df 598. It shows that there is a highly statistically significant difference in the modernization of college going tribal students of hill and plain area in terms of education dimension. The mean values show that tribal students of plain area are more modernized in terms of education dimension as compared to the students of hill area.

On the other hand, at df 598 the obtained t-values for modernization in terms of socio-religious dimension ($t = 1.598$), marriage dimension ($t = 0.486$) and position of women dimension ($t = 1.492$) have not been found significant even at 0.05 level of significance. It shows that there is no significant difference in the modernization of college going tribal students of hill and plain area in terms of socio-religious dimension, marriage dimension and position of women dimension.

It may be concluded that only one t-value is found significant while three t-values are found insignificant. Thus, the null hypothesis that *“There will be no significant difference in the modernization of college going female tribal students of hill and plain area”* is partly rejected and mostly accepted.

To compare the modernization of college going female tribal students of science and non-science stream.

Table – 5: Comparison of Modernization of College going Female Tribal Students of Science and Non-Science Stream

Dimensions of Modernization	Stream	Mean	S.D.	Df	t-value	Result
Socio-Religious	Science	28.07	7.87	598	1.531	NS
	Non-Science	27.25	6.94			
Marriage	Science	27.84	7.87	598	0.390	NS
	Non-Science	27.61	6.97			
Position of Women	Science	30.31	10.02	598	0.056	NS
	Non-Science	30.27	8.72			
Education	Science	28.31	8.63	598	2.115*	S
	Non-Science	26.94	7.16			

S = Significant

* = Significant at 0.05 Level of Significance. NS = Not Significant

The table no. 5 presents the comparison of modernization of college going tribal students of science and non-science stream. The obtained t-values for modernization in terms of education dimension ($t = 2.115$) has been found significant at 0.05 level of significance at df 598. It shows that there is a significant difference in the modernization of college going tribal students of science and non-science stream in terms of education dimension. The mean values show that tribal students of science stream are more modernized in terms of education dimension as compared to the students of non-science stream.

On the other hand, at df 598 the obtained t-values for modernization in terms of socio-religious dimension ($t = 1.531$), marriage dimension ($t = 0.390$) and position of women dimension ($t = 0.056$) have not been found significant even at 0.05 level of significance. It shows that there is no significant difference in the modernization of college going tribal students of science and non-science stream in terms of socio-religious dimension, marriage dimension and position of women dimension.

It may be concluded that only one t-value is found significant while three t-values are found insignificant. Thus, the null hypothesis that *“There will be no significant difference in the modernization of college going female tribal students of science and non-science stream”* is partly rejected and mostly accepted.

Findings

1. Female tribal students of hill area were highly modernized in terms of position of women dimension while they were least modernized in terms of education dimension. On the other hand, female tribal students of plain area were highly modernized in terms of position of women dimension while they were least modernized in terms socio-religious dimension.
2. Female tribal students of science stream were highly modernized in terms of position of women dimension while they were least modernized in terms of marriage dimension. On the other hand, female tribal students of non-science stream were highly modernized in terms of position of women dimension while they were least modernized in terms of education dimension.
3. There was found a significant difference in the modernization of female tribal students of hill and plain area in terms of education dimension. Female tribal students of plain area were found more modernized in terms of education dimension as compared to the students of hill area. But no significant difference was found in the modernization of female tribal students of hill and plain area in terms of socio-religious dimension, marriage dimension and position of women dimension.

4. A significant difference was found in the modernization of female tribal students of science and non-science stream in terms of education dimension. Female tribal students of science stream were more modernized in terms of education dimension as compared to the students of non-science stream. But no significant difference was found in the modernization of female tribal students of science and non-science stream in terms of socio-religious dimension, marriage dimension and position of women dimension.

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